

Happiness Understanding Depending on Features of Coping Behavior

A.R.Rizulla, F.S.Tashimova, A.R. Massalimova, A.K.Mynbayeva, G.S.Abdiraimova

Abstract—The importance of happiness understanding research is caused by cardinal changes experiences in system of people values in the post-Soviet countries territory. «The time of changes», which characterized with destruction of old values and not creativeness of new, stimulating experiences by the person of existential vacuum. The given research is actual not only in connection with sense formation, but also in connection with necessity creatively to adapt in integrative space. According to numerous works [1,2,3], we define happiness as the peak experience connected with satisfaction correlated system of needs, dependent on style of subject's coping behavior.

Keywords—Coping behavior, happiness, overcoming, psychological defense.

I. INTRODUCTION

HAPPINESS understanding and the factors providing the given phenomenon rather variously. In many works the happiness is defined as the general satisfaction of life dependent on a realization measure in various spheres [1], as the pleasure received from realization of intense requirement depending on libido movement [2], the achievements provided with fruitfulness [3]. Defining happiness as the peak experiences connected with satisfaction of needs system, we consider that it depends on the main integrating and correcting force of all correlation of the subject in sense formation process— from copying behavior style. Thus, all internal and external indicators are fixed. The copying behavior we understand as steady ways system of personal behavior, unconscious protective strategy defined by a parity and purposeful overcoming strategy of various life difficulties.

To proof our hypothesis, we had been conducted research directed on revealing of given dependence.

II. PROCEDURE

A. Methods

Please According to hypothesis following methods were used in the research: 1. Frydenberg, E., Lewis, R. Adolescent

Rizulla A.R., department of Psychology, Al-Farabi Kazakh National University, Almaty Kazakhstan master of psychology (phone: +7(727) 8(727) 251 97 50; e-mail: Aidana.r2010@mail.ru).

Tashimova F.S., department of Psychology, Al-Farabi Kazakh National University, Almaty Kazakhstan, professor, doctor of psychological sciences (phone: +7(727)3773333 (1339); e-mail: fatima_tashimova@mail.ru).

Mynbayeva A.K., department of Pedagogy, Al-Farabi Kazakh National University, Almaty Kazakhstan as professor doctor of pedagogical sciences (phone: +7 (727) 2453413; e-mail: umo200709@mail.ru).

Massalimova A.R., dean of the faculty Al-Farabi Kazakh National University, Almaty Kazakhstan as professor doctor of philosophical sciences (phone: +7 (727) 2671516; e-mail: Jameliya10@mail.ru).

Abdiraimova G.S. department of Sociology, Al-Farabi Kazakh National University, Almaty Kazakhstan as professor doctor of social sciences (phone: 8(727)3773333 (1349); e-mail: Gulmira.Abdiraimova@kaznu.kz).

(Coping Scale - ACS), adapted by T.N.Krjukova [4] -method of incomplete offers on happiness understanding, the method of «Actual sense», developed by authors [5].

B. Subjects

There were 252 students investigated in general. In data analyzing were used: the factor analysis, a method of the main components; the objective analysis. These data analyzing methods allowed us to group subjects by level of factor expressiveness, and also the semantic analysis developed by one of authors [6].

C. Results

As a result of data analyzing 4 factors have been revealed:

TABLE I
ILLUSTRATED REFLECTION OF THE FACTORS

The factor 1 is presented by the following indicators reflecting those or other coping strategy: Focusing on the problems decision (0,635). Needs for social support, discussion of a problem with other people on purpose to secure with their approval and support - (- 607); Persistent work and achievements - (0,583); Dispassionateness, unwillingness to devote others in the cares - (0,561); Self-accusations, the strict relation to, sensation of a private problems responsibility - (0,522); Ignoring, conscious blocking of a problem (-0,491); Productive leisure (playing sports, health maintenance - (- 0,472); Orientation to religious support - (0,405). A discharge (tears, aggression, alcohol, drugs) - (0,382).

The factor 2 is presented by indicators with following factorial scales: Success in study and achievements - (0,752); the Optimistic view on actual problem - (0,698); Considering of a problem from different points of view and the decision (0,499); the Rate on close friends - (0, 482); Active resting (playing sports, health maintenance) - (0,470). Derivations, entertainments in a society - (0,467); the Organization of public actions - (0,379); Anxiety and uneasiness on

consequences – (-0,437); Self-accusations, responsibility acceptance on itself (0,385);

The greatest loadings in the factor 3 have following indicators:

Dispassionateness, refusal to devote others in the cares – (0,554); the Discharge – (tears, aggression, alcohol, drugs) - (0,537); Orientation to religious support – (0,513); Hopes of a happy occurrence – (0,455); Success in study and achievements - (0,413); Anxiety, uneasiness for consequences – (0,403); Self-accusations, responsibility acceptance on itself – (0,390); problem Ignoring, their conscious blocking (0,308).

The factor 4 is presented by following indicators: Requirement for social support – (0,674); Feeling of an accessory and search of their approval – (0,642); the Support on close friends – (0,533); Success in study and achievements – (-0,507); Hope of a happy occurrence – (0,504); Refusal of actions, up to painful conditions – (0,491); problem Ignoring, its conscious blocking – (- 0,473); Dispassionateness, refusal to devote others in the cares – (- 455); Orientation to religious support – (0,446).

III. DISCUSSION

The analysis of indicators allows ascertaining that in the given coping strategy factor, reflecting mobility and independence in the decision of the life problems, assuming dispassionateness from intervention of others prevail. In this case, dispassionateness strategy can be understood as high concentrations on purposes achievement and concentration on the problems decision, own responsibility connected with comprehension for result. That is, dispassionateness in this case, reflects deepness in a problem solution, self-sufficiency of the subject focused on personal growth. The given factor reflects high enough level of subject's self-regulation, more using the overcoming of difficult reality situations strategy, at the limited system of coping ways of protective character. The egotism is most used defense mechanisms as a high level of self-control. Pressure from high concentration overcomes by different defense mechanisms, such as discharge (tears, aggression, more often, directed on itself). Unfortunately, the given factor reflects some ignoring of body care problems, directed on restoring of the forces connected with active rest. According to above, it is possible to tell that the given strategy parity allows to define the given factor as problem-oriented coping style, corresponded with "mobile" style. By results of the objective analysis 25 % of students characterized by high level of given factor expressiveness. The happiness is defined by them as achievement. The analysis of second factor indicators allows us to ascertain it as orientation on own system self-effectiveness in overcoming of difficult reality situations, also as an account, and correlation to meaningful positions of others. That is, they are capable on joint activity while decision of difficult reality situations, in difference of the group 1 students, who focused only on themselves. Besides, the indicators analysis allows us to ascertain students' successful regulation of achievements processes and comfort, and also overcoming and expedient protection. The indicators

analysis allows to give a name of the given factor, as reflecting "harmonious" coping style. For students, with high level of the given factor expressiveness (only 29% persons) characterized the understanding of happiness as sensation and harmony creation. The analysis of the third factor indicators allows to ascertain a dominating role of dispassionateness. However dispassionateness in the given factor connected not much with concentration on the problems decision, how many on necessity of a discharge. In this case, dispassionateness acts as the protective strategy connected with "leaving" to internal world. Dispassionateness from the surrounding social world stimulates the importance of the intimate interlocutor in the name of god by which support students of the given group are guided. Besides, the orientation to a miracle has important value for them. Despite sufficient level of success in studying, their internal world is often shaken from uncertainty, from self-accusations that stimulates not much as problem solution, as its blocking. Uncertainty also generates an Ions complex. Thus, in the given coping style the defense strategy defines the role of dispassionateness from others. In this connection, we named the given factor as emotionally-focused or reflecting "egocentric" coping style. Students, with high level of the given factor expressiveness (only 14 %) understand happiness as love. The analysis of the fourth factor indicators allows to conclude significant relation of the subject with others and orientation to their support in process of life difficulties overcoming. According to research results there is a little underestimated comprehension of own self-efficiency. Overcoming is perceived as the situation decision with the "whole world" that reflects the prevalence such strategy as running from responsibility, orientation to the help of others. Results allow to name the given factor as socially-focused coping style or «sociocentric». Students with high level of the given factor expressiveness (only 36 %) understand happiness as pleasures.

IV. CONCLUSION

The analysis of the results show the correlation of understanding happiness from the style of coping behavior, as corrective process of sense formation. Thus, for the students with mobile style of coping behavior the understanding of the happiness as a achievement is more applicable. For the students with problem oriented style of coping behavior provided by equal parity of overcoming strategy and defense strategy, the understanding of happiness as a harmony creation in various life situations. For the students with egocentric style of coping behavior understanding of happiness as love is more applicable. In this case, love plays role of compensatory of inadaptivity in social life. For students of social oriented style of coping behavior the understanding of happiness comes as achieving the pleasure.

REFERENCES

- [1] Argayl M. Psychology of happiness. 2nd Ed. SP.b: Piter, 2003.- 271 p. (in Russian language)
- [2] Freud S. Dissatisfaction of culture //Basic instinct/Moscow.: Olymp: OOO «AST-LTD edition», 1997, p.431 – 512 (in Russian language)

- [3] Fromm E. Running from freedom. Human for himself. //translated to russian. Moscow.: «AST-LTD edition», 2004. – 571 p. (in Russian language)
- [4] Krukova T.L. Methods of coping behavior research: three coping - scales.- Kostroma: Avntitul, 2007. - 60 p. (in Russian language).
- [5] Tashimova F.S., Rizulla A.R. Features of virtual subjects influence on creative adaptation and experiences of youth happiness in globalization conditions // Intercultural mutual relations in Kazakhstan in the globalization process. Almaty, 2011, p.149-156. (in Russian language)
- [6] Tashimova F.S. The psychological analysis of subject determination of senses. Almaty: « Kazakh University», 2011, Monography in Russian language. 287 p.